

Title: **Compilation of existing in-situ and remote ground based observations**
Deliverable number: **D5.1**
Revision 1 - Status: **Final**
Date of issue: **31/05/2019**

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Deliverable number	D5.1
Revision	1
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	31/12/2018
Date of issue	31/05/2019
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	MPI-M
Dissemination level	PU (Public)

*This work has received research funding from the European Union
H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 Programme under grant agreement n° 777544.*

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1. List of ground-based observation networks in the LAC region

The following table provides a detailed list of available ground-based observation networks in different countries in the LAC region that can be potentially used within the PAPILA project in particular for validation of the model simulations and forecasts that are under preparation. As it can be seen, some networks (e.g. SINCA, SISAIRE) provide observations of several major air pollutants since already more than a decade and can thus provide valuable information on air pollution changes in the corresponding countries during the last decades. Some other networks (e.g. RMCAB) were established however only recently. Several of the observational datasets have public access through dedicated websites. Contact persons are provided for datasets that require grant access or that have specific restrictions.

This list of available datasets is compiled in close collaboration with several PAPILA partners in the LAC region. It will be made available to all partners through the project website and will be further completed with new details and information during the course of the project as soon as we are aware of any changes and/or new datasets.

Country (City)	Name of network/facility	Species available	Available time period	Maintenance Organisation	Link to data	Accessibility	Information source
Chile	Sistema de Informacion Nacional de Calidad del Aire (SINCA)	PM 2.5, PM 10, SO ₂ , NO ₂ , NO _x , NO, CO, O ₃ , CH ₄ , HCNM	1997*-present	Ministerio del Medio Ambiente, Gobierno de Chile	https://sinca.ma.gob.cl/	Public access	Laura Gallardo (lgallard@u.uchile.cl), Camilo Menares (cmenares@dgf.uchile.cl)
Colombia	Subsistema de Infomacion sobre Calidad de Aire	PM10, SO2, O3	1998*-present	Instituto de Hidrología, Meteorología y	http://www.sisai.re.gov.co:8080/faces/portal/defa	Public access	Nestor Y. Rojas (nyrojasr@una

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Colombia	(SISAIRE) SISAIRE		Estudios Ambientales (Ideam), Adscrito al Ministerio de Ambiente, Vivienda y Desarrollo Territorial de Colombia. Dataset from Nestor Rojas	ult.jsp https://drive.google.com/uc?id=11eDRwtY2YjaW-Xq1ObTCcqo7gal7w_BM&export=download	Access from Google drive	l.edu.co) Nestor Y. Rojas (nyrojasr@unal.edu.co)
Colombia (Bogota)	Red de Monitoreo de Calidad del Aire de Bogota (RMCAB)	PM10, CO, O3, NO, NO2, NOX, PM2.5	Secretaría Distrital de Ambiente, Bogota, Colombia	http://201.245.192.252:81/	Public access	Nestor Y. Rojas (nyrojasr@unal.edu.co)
Colombia (Bogota)	RMCAB		Dataset from Universidad Nacional de Colombia	https://login.unal.edu.co/cloudkey/a/unal.edu.co/user/login?name=space=unal.edu.co	Access grant necessary from University	Nestor Y. Rojas (nyrojasr@unal.edu.co)
Colombia	Sistema de Alerta	PM2.5,	Empresas Públicas	https://siata.gov.co	Public access	Nestor Y.

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(Medellin)	Temprana de Medellín y el Valle de Aburrá (SIATA)	PM10, O3, NO2, CO, SO2, BC		de Medellín and ISAGEN	co/siata_nuevo/		Rojas (nyrojasr@una l.edu.co)
Mexico	Sistema Nacional de Información de la Calidad del Aire (SINAICA)	CO, SO2, NO2, NO, Nox, O3, PM10, PM2.5	2009* - present	Instituto Nacional de Ecología y Cambio Climático	https://sinaica.in ecc.gob.mx/data .php	Public access	José Agustín García Reynoso (agustin@atmo sfera.unam.mx)
Mexico (Central Mexico)		CO, NO2, NO, NOX, O3, SO2, PM10, PM2.5	1986 – present	Secretaria del medio ambiente, Gobierno de la ciudad de Mexico	http://www.aire. cdmx.gob.mx/d efault.php?opc= %27aKBhnmI= %27&opcion=Z g==	Public access	José Agustín García Reynoso (agustin@atmo sfera.unam.mx)
Puerto Rico	AirNow	O3, PM10, PM2.5. AQI		Junta de Calidad Ambiental de Puerto Rico	http://www.age ncias.pr.gov/age ncias/jca/Pages/ indiceaire.aspx	Public access	

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Puerto Rico (Pico del Este, Cape San Juan, University of Puerto-Rico-Rio Piedras)	PDE, CSJ, UPRRP	See additional information	See additional information	University of Puerto-Rico-Rio Piedras	See additional information	Access from UPRRP	Olga Mayol (omayol@ites.upr.edu)
Argentina (Buenos Aires)		CO, NO2, PM10	2009*-present	Gobierno de la Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires	https://www.buenosaires.gob.ar/agenciaambiental/controlambiental	Public access	Espada, Ramiro (ramiro.espada@mpimet.mpg.de)
Argentina (Bahia Blanca)		CO, O3, SO2, NO, NO2, NOX, PM10,	2010-2015	Municipio de Bahia Blanca	http://datos.bahiaablanca.gob.ar/search/?q=calidad+aire	Public access	Espada, Ramiro (ramiro.espada@mpimet.mpg.de)

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Argentina (Mendoza)	las estaciones fijas manuales del microcentro de la Provincia de Mendoza	NO, NO2, NOX, SO2, PM10	2016-2017	Área de Contaminación Atmosférica de la Dirección de Protección Ambiental, Secretaría de Ambiente y Ordenamiento Territorial	http://datosabiertos.mendoza.gov.ar/dataset/calidad-del-aire	Public access	Espada, Ramiro (ramiro.espada@mpimet.mpg.de)
Argentina (Mendoza)	Measurement by the automatic mobile unit located in Calle San Martín and Virgen del Carmen de Cuyo.	NO, NO2, NOX, PM10, O3	2016-2018	Área de Contaminación Atmosférica de la Dirección de Protección Ambiental, Secretaría de Ambiente y Ordenamiento Territorial	http://datosabiertos.mendoza.gov.ar/dataset/calidad-del-aire	Public access	Espada, Ramiro (ramiro.espada@mpimet.mpg.de)
Uruguay (Montevideo)	Red de monitoreo de la calidad del aire de Montevideo	PM2.5, PM10, SO2, NO2, O3, BC, PM total	2015-2016	La Intendencia de Montevideo	https://catalogo.datos.gub.uy/tr/dataset/red-de-monitoreo-de-la-calidad-del-aire-de-montevideo	Public access	Espada, Ramiro (ramiro.espada@mpimet.mpg.de)

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Bolivia	Sistema Nacional de Infomacion Ambiental (SNIA)	PM10	2009*-2016	Ministerio de Medio Ambiente y Agua, Bolivia	http://snia.mma.gob.bo/web/modulos/PNGC/A/	Public access	http://aqicn.org/faq/2015-05-10/a-comparison-of-latin-american-air-quality-scales/
Brazil	Sistema Nacional do Meio Ambiente (SISNAMA)	PM10, PM2.5, PMtotal, SO2, CO, O3, NO, NO2, Smoke (Fumaça?)	2000-2017	Ministério do Meio Ambiente (MMA)	http://qualidadeoar.org.br/	Public access	Vinicius Mateus (vinicius.mateus@mpimet.mpg.de)
Peru (Lima)	Sistema de Gestión de Información de la Calidad del Aire en Peru (SENAMHI)	PM2.5, PM10, SO2, NO2, O3, CO	2010*-present	Ministerio del Ambiente	https://www.senamhi.gob.pe/?p=calidad-del-aire	Public access	http://aqicn.org/faq/2015-05-10/a-comparison-of-latin-american-air-quality-scales/

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Ecuador (Quito)	Red de Monitoreo atmosferico	CO, NO2, O3, PM10, PM2.5, SO2	2007-2019 (emission inventory also available for year 2003,2005,2007, 2009 and 2011)	Secretaria de Ambiente	http://www.quitoambiente.gob.ec/ambiente/index.php/reportes-calidad-del-aire-y-meteorologia	Public access	http://aqicn.org/faq/2015-05-10/a-comparison-of-latin-american-air-quality-scales/
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* - depends on the establishment of individual stations

2. Additional information on observation facilities in individual countries

This section provides some additional information on some observation facilities in some individual countries that could be useful for the different partners in PAPILA.

Chile: Data from Chile are found at <https://sinca.mma.gob.cl/>

Under "INFORMACION HISTORICA" you find all data for all stations.

These data are reported as "registros validados", "registros preliminares" and "registros no validados". Validados means checked by system and a responsible person; preliminares have been subject to systems checking (no person involved), and no validados are raw data. There is a description of these data as well as a sampled of these data plus recommendations for further checking in <https://www.elementscience.org/articles/10.1525/elementa.293/> (Supp. Material)

Puerto Rico: (by Dr. Olga L. Mayol-Bracero)

PICO DEL ESTE, PDE (ALSO KNOWN AS EAST PEAK, EP) (18° 16' N, 65° 45' W, 1051 M AMSL)

Pico del Este station, managed by Dr. Mayol-Bracero, was totally demolished by Hurricane Maria. Prior to the hurricane, the following instruments were deployed at PE: two weather stations, a single-stage aluminum Caltech active strand cloud water collector, a visibility sensor (Belfort 6100), a liquid water sensor (LWC-100, DMT), a back-scatter cloud probe (BCP, DMT), and two high-volume filter samplers.

Presently, PDE has available a liquid water sensor (LWC-100, DMT) and a back-scatter cloud probe (BCP, DMT), both of which escaped damage because they were out for maintenance; all the other instruments were destroyed. After the hurricane, the company Droplet Measurement Technologies donated a brand new Wideband Integrated Bioaerosol Sensor (WIBS-NEO) and Magee Scientific donated a refurbished model AE-31 aethalometer for measurement of equivalent black carbon. Also, Jeff Collett, through Colorado State University (CSU), is donating one of his new CASCC2 cloud water collectors that will replace the one that was destroyed by hurricane Maria.

Through funding from our NSF RAPID (NUMBER and title), NSF MRI (NUMBER and title) and NSF (EAR-1331841 - Luquillo CZO: The role of hot spots and hot moments in tropical landscape evolution and functioning of the critical zone) we have been able to acquire the following:

- 1) Three modified 20' steel shipping containers, one will be used as a storage room and office space and the other two are the aerosol and cloud laboratories.
- 2) replacements of materials and instruments destroyed by Hurricane Maria: visibility sensor (Vaisala PWD), weather station (WXT530, Vaisala), three dehumidifiers, one size-resolved hi-vol sampler (TISCH TE-6070), one pH meter, one conductivity meter, backup power generator and battery storage, and a data acquisition system.

- 3) upgrades to the instrumentation that existed prior to the hurricane include a dry/wet deposition sampler (NADP Teflon Pad approved for NTN Network), a pyranometer (CMP-3, Vaisala), an Optical Particle Counter (OPC; GRIMM 1.109), an anemometer able to sustain hurricane-force winds (WMT703, Vaisala), a Beta Attenuation Particulate Monitor (BAMS; 1020, Met One) to monitor PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ mass concentrations, a 3-wave nephelometer (Aurora3000, American Ecotech), and a precipitation monitor (NMO191, Eigenbrodt).
- 4) Other upgrades associated specifically to the ACAS project include the following instruments: the SP2 (XR, Droplet Measurement Technologies), Ground-based Counterflow Virtual Impactor Inlet System (GCVI, Brechtel), a Scanning Electrical Mobility Spectrometer (SEMS; 2100; Brechtel), a cloud condensation nuclei counter (CNN-100, Droplet Measurement Technologies [DMT]), and a Tunable Diode Laser Hygrometer (TDL, DMT). In 2020 we will also purchase an aerosol chemical speciation monitor (TOF-ACSEM, Aerodyne Research Inc).

CAPE SAN JUAN, CSJ, ALSO KNOWN AS CPR (18⁰ 23' N, 65⁰ 37' W, 60 M AMSL)

CSJ is a WMO GAW regional station, a NASA AERONET station (since 2004), part of the NOAA ESRL's aerosol federated network (since 2004), and a future NASA MPLNET station (starting July this year). CSJ, managed by Dr. Mayol-Bracero (UPRRP), was also severely damaged by Hurricane Maria. Some repairs at no cost to some of the damaged instruments was done by NOAA ESRL as well as by Magee Scientific. A proposal from NASA GSFC was approved for the reconstruction of this station. Also, a DOE ARM steel container was approved to support this station, this was installed in July of 2018. Since then, we resumed some of the operations at the station. We already have installed and sampling a weather station (WXT530, Vaisala), an anemometer able to sustain hurricane-force winds (WMT703, Vaisala), a pyranometer (CMP-3, Vaisala), a 3-wavelength integrating nephelometer (Model 3563, TSI), an aethalometer (AE-31 Magee Scientific), a 3-wavelength continuous light absorption photometer (CLAP, NOAA), a condensation particle counter (3772, TSI), a sunphotometer (CE318-N, CIMEL) that is part of the AERONET (<http://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov>), a PANDORA spectrometer part of the Pandonia Global Network (<https://pandora.gsfc.nasa.gov>), several filter and impactor samplers (i.e., three stacked-filter units, one size-resolved (PM₁₀ /PM_{2.5}) Hi Vol samplers and another Total Suspended Particles Hi-volume). Other instruments that are available for this station and that will be soon installed are: an Optical Particle Counter (OPC; GRIMM 1.109), a Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS; TSI 3936), and a Dekati low-pressure impactor (Dekati Ltd., Micro Orifice Uniform Deposition Impactor, MOUDI, TSP). DOE-ARM has also lent us another cloud condensation nuclei counter (CNN-100, Droplet Measurement Technologies) for this site.

UNIVERSITY OF PUERTO RICO – RÍO PIEDRAS (UPRRP).

The Atmospheric Chemistry and Aerosol Research (ACAR) Laboratory under the direction of Dr. Mayol-Bracero is equipped with an EC/OC analyzer (Sunset Lab), an Ion Chromatograph

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(Metrohm 850 Professional IC with a 896 Professional Detector), and a TOC/TN analyzer (Shimadzu TOC-5000A). Also aerosol sampling at this facility currently includes the MIPS (an OPC and CPC combined unit developed and lent by the Max Plank Institute for Chemistry). Here we will also install before September the following: a weather station (WXT530, Vaisala) and an anemometer able to sustain hurricane-force winds (WMT703, Vaisala). With our active NASA-ROSES project, we will purchase this year an environmental chamber to perform gravimetric analysis while controlling for RH and temperature (5532, ETS).

At UPR-RP, Mayol-Bracero also has access to a Machine Shop, Glass Blowing facilities, Material Characterization Center of the College of Natural Sciences at UPRRP, and to the research and administrative facilities of the Department of Environmental Science.